

Computational validation and multiplier effects on tritium production in hybrid reactor blanket mock-up

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Academic editor: Osama Ashraf ♦ Received 9 December 2024 ♦ Accepted 20 February 2025 ♦ Published 18 March 2025

Citation: Ishraq MdAR, Roy S, Afanasiev VV (2025) Computational validation and multiplier effects on tritium production in hybrid reactor blanket mock-up. Nuclear Energy and Technology 11(1): 71–77. <https://doi.org/10.3897/nucet.11.143957>

Abstract

In this study, a simplified computational model of the blanket mock-up is created using the SERPENT Monte Carlo Code. The nuclear data is obtained from the enriched ENDF/B.VII.1 data library to conduct this study. The model is validated, as the error percentage for $^{63}\text{Cu}(n,2n)^{62}\text{Cu}$ and $^{65}\text{Cu}(n,2n)^{64}\text{Cu}$ reactions is less than 10% when compared to experimental results. The computational model is used to calculate the tritium production rate in different lithium zones with various neutron multipliers (U, Pb) and without any multipliers. The results show that the tritium production rate with a uranium multiplier is 86% higher than with a lead multiplier and 238% higher than with no multiplier. The neutron energy spectrum shows a peak in the 0.1 MeV to 10 MeV energy range for every case. This study also examines the effects of fusion neutrons on different isotopes, providing valuable data on how materials behave under high-speed neutron exposure.

Keywords

Hybrid Reactor Blanket, SERPENT model Validation, Multiplier, Tritium production

Introduction

Fusion technology is regarded as the most environmentally friendly option, offering unlimited fuel availability (ITER 2024). The most economically effective fusion reaction involves deuterium and tritium. Tritium can be produced by bombarding the Li-6 isotope with neutrons. The global abundance of the Li-6 isotope is 7.8% (Kondev et al. 2021). The hybrid reactor blanket multiplier concept is proposed to improve the economic feasibility of fusion reactors. Theoretical studies and experiments on fusion reactor concepts focus on confining plasma generated under extreme temperature and pressure conditions. Meanwhile, approximately 440 nuclear fission reactors are operating worldwide (Statista 2024). Despite the rapid

advancements in fission reactor technology, challenges persist regarding waste management, safety, and the mitigation of proliferation risks (Zheng et al. 2012).

A promising solution to address these issues is the hybrid reactor, which combines the principles of nuclear fusion and fission for power generation (Bedenko et al. 2022). The core idea of a hybrid reactor lies in utilizing the fast neutrons produced by fusion reactions to bombard fertile isotopes, thereby sustaining a fission process. The deuterium-tritium (D-T) fusion reaction stands as one of the most extensively studied fusion processes (Bedenko et al. 2022; Lindecker 2024). The reaction is given by,

The released neutron from the aforementioned fusion reaction possesses an average energy of 14.1 MeV, categorizing it as a fast neutron (Ericsson 2019). Then the emitted fast neutron causes fission in the multiplier region. The layer of fertile isotope in the blanket zone is called the multiplier. The chain reaction cannot be sustained because there are no fissile isotopes in the multiplier region. The fusion reactor blanket with a multiplier can generate energy, facilitate waste transmutation, and breed nuclear fuel (Afanasiev et al. 1996; Zheng et al. 2012; Ericsson 2019; Bedenko et al. 2022a, 2022b; Lindecker 2024).

There are recent works available on fusion energy focusing on the ITER and its tritium breeding capability (Lian et al. 2023). Transuranic material is utilized in the blanket region of a hybrid reactor, where a Tokamak fusion reactor serves as the neutron source and Li17-Pb83 functions as the coolant. The test results demonstrate the viability of the hybrid reactor concept (Stacey et al. 2002; Stacey 2009). Research is currently being conducted to investigate the design of a hybrid reactor through the analysis of neutronic and thermal-hydraulic aspects (Strebkov et al. 2009; Kulikov et al. 2020; Shi et al. 2020; Bedenko et al. 2023). Japan demonstrates that a thermal blanket utilizing light water as a coolant is applicable for the ITER fusion source. Th-U fuel cycle is also explored in further studies (Murata et al. 2005, 2007; Matsunaka et al. 2007; Cui et al. 2017). Advancements have also occurred in theoretical research regarding fuel breeding and transmutation (Lian et al. 2020). Several conceptual designs have been proposed based on EAST and ITER fusion sources in China (Wu 2002). In 2010, China initiated a project under the National Magnetic Confinement Fusion Science Program (Wu et al. 2006; Chio et al. 2010). The objective is to propose an appropriate blanket design for energy multiplication. The research focuses on the ITER-like fusion source (Jiang et al. 2010; Zhou et al. 2011).

This study establishes a computational model utilizing a three-dimensional Monte Carlo algorithm and the neutronic code SERPENT to analyze the impact of neutron multipliers on blanket mock-up design. Computational modeling plays a crucial role in forecasting future events and exploring the underlying reasons for those occurrences. Another advantage of computational modeling over experimental research is the amount of money and resources required to set up an experiment. Computational modeling plays a crucial role in enhancing and improving the efficiency of an experimental facility (Calder et al. 2018). The main focus will be on increasing the number of neutrons using the multiplier. The increased neutron count would generate fusion seed Tritium in three distinct lithium regions to sustain the fusion process.

Methods and methodology

Computational modeling of hybrid reactor blanket mock-up

The computational model is developed using the SERPENT Monte Carlo Algorithm. Three types of blanket mock-ups are designed. The first one is designed using a uranium

multiplier, the second one is designed using a lead multiplier, and the third one is designed without any multiplier.

The design parameters for each type of blanket mock-up configuration are taken from the experimental facility (Afanasiev et al. 1996). The dimension of each layer is given in the Table 1. The lithium zones in the blanket mock-up are divided into two types of blocks. One is 2 cm thick and another is 4 cm thick. Every block contains a different atomic density. The density of the LiAl alloy for every zone is shown in Table 2 considering 2.45% lithium by mass (Joshi 2007). The structural diagram showing each layer of the blanket mock-up with a uranium multiplier is given in Fig. 1. To construct this computational model some simplified assumptions are being considered. They are:

- The source from where fusion neutron is emitted is considered as a point source since the geometry of the external source is complex. The considered point source is 15 cm away from the first wall of the blanket
- The detectors holder part which are used to hold detector in different coordinate position to measure reaction rate, and tritium production rate at the intersection of walls are not taken into consideration.

During the computational design of fusion reactors, validating design parameters involves verifying neutron codes and data through calculations based on integral benchmark experiments using a 14.75 MeV neutron source and all the simplification assumptions are taken into consideration in respect to the experimental facility.

Figure 1. Simplified diagram of hybrid blanket mock-up.

Computational workflow

Subsequent calculations of the computational model about the tritium generation rate and neutron activation rate of various isotopes will be considered if the calculated values show an error percentage of less than 10% (Afanasiev et al. 1996). The simulation workflow is given in Fig. 2. The detector's position for this computation is regarded as relative to the blanket wall. All the calculation is conducted by considering the first wall at $x = 0$ position with vacuum

Table 1. Transversal dimensions of blanket mock-up for uranium and lead multiplier (Afanasiev et al. 1996)

Component	Material	Thickness (cm)
First wall	Stainless steel	1
Multiplier	Uranium/Lead	5/10
First lithium zone	LiAl alloy	6
Moderator	Plexiglas	2.1
Second lithium zone	LiAl alloy	14
Moderator	Plexiglas	1.9
Third lithium zone	LiAl alloy	4
Moderator	Plexiglas	1.9
Shielding Materials	Stainless steel	10.1
	Plexiglas	3.3
	Stainless steel	2

Table 2. Density and width of every LiAl block in the lithium zones (Afanasiev et al. 1996)

Lithium zone	Width (cm)	Density (kg/cm ³)
First lithium zone	2	2625
	4	2610
Second lithium zone	2	2625
	4	2665
	4	2616
	4	2670
Third lithium zone	2	2625
	2	2616

boundary condition. For the blanket mockup model, the vacuum boundary condition is also set. This simulation tracks 900,000,000 neutrons over 1,000 cycles and the cross-section data are sourced from ENDF/B.VII.1 library.

Result and discussion

Computational validation

The computational model is validated with respect to the experimental value. The comparison between experimental data and computational data is provided with respect to the relative activation rate of Cu-63 and Cu-65 isotope provided in Figs 3, 4. The relative activation rate is calculated by taking ratio for every obtained value of detector coordinate with respect to the initial value obtained at initial position of detector. The average uncertainty obtained for Cu-63 activation is 3.63% while it is 6% for the activation of Cu-65 isotope. Since the error percentage is less than 10%, the computational model validated the experimental data (Afanasiev et al. 1996; Tonghua et al. 2019; Thompson et al. 2021).

Copper activation has served as a conventional method for calculating neutron yields in DT fusion experiments for over 30 years. The primary focus is on the $^{63}\text{Cu}(n,2n)^{62}\text{Cu}$ and $^{65}\text{Cu}(n,2n)^{64}\text{Cu}$ reaction (Glebov et al. 2006).

Tritium production rate

There are three separate lithium zones after the neutron generated from fusion passes the multiplier zone. The work of the lithium zone is to produce tritium using the reaction,

The neutron multiplier is used to enhance the number of neutrons so that the tritium production rate can be increased. Since the prompt fission cross-section of U-238 is 0.644 barns with a neutron energy of 14.75 MeV is much higher compared to the elastic cross-section for Pb-208, which is 4.9×10^{-21} barns at the same energy level, the neutron generation rate for uranium multiplier will be highest (Soppera et al. 2014). Thus, the tritium generation rate for the use of the uranium multiplier would also be higher. Fig. 5 advocates the argument that the normalized neutron flux over the neutron energy range is the highest in the case of the uranium multiplier. Due to a higher cross-section, this study observes a peak in the neutron number for the use of uranium multiplier in the 0.1 to 10 MeV energy range. The average fission neutron energy is 0.1 to 10 MeV. With higher neutron flux, the uranium multiplier will avail more neutrons to the Li-zone which will increase overall tritium production.

Figure 3. Relative activation rate of Cu-63(n,2n).

Figure 4. Relative activation rate of Cu-65(n,2n).

Fig. 6 represents that the cross-section for ${}^6\text{Li}(n,\alpha)\text{T}$ reaction is the highest within the energy range 200–300 KeV of neutrons. That is why it is important to slow down the neutrons that are emitted after the reaction with the multiplier. Thus, the moderator is used to maximize the tritium production rate.

Table 2 shows that the three different lithium zones are divided into different regions of LiAl with varying atomic densities of Li-6, Li-7, and Al isotopes. Lower density of alloy means higher atomic density for Li-6 and Li-7 isotopes. Since the share of lithium is considered a constant value for every LiAl region. That is the reason why the U-shaped curve is observed in the case of observing the tritium production rate Fig. 7. Furthermore, the excessive moderation decreased the tritium production rate in the third lithium zone, though the densities of LiAl are not much higher in that zone. In the first lithium zone, the tritium production rate is the highest in the region where LiAl density is the lowest. This is similar for the second and third lithium zones as well. There is another factor that influences the tritium

Figure 5. Normalized neutron flux for the use of different multipliers.

production rate, which is the width of the lithium-containing regions. Increased width increases the probability of interaction between neutrons and lithium atoms. For this reason, in the second lithium zone, the tritium production rate is the highest cumulatively.

In the case of a uranium multiplier, when a neutron reacts with uranium fission occurs. Since the amount of energy from the prompt fission reaction remains in the range of 100 KeV to 10 MeV the average prompt neutron energy is 700 KeV (Madland 1982). At that range the ${}^6\text{Li}(n,\alpha)\text{T}$ reaction probability is also high. Therefore, in the first Li zone, the tritium production rate is maximum. Though it is reduced in the second it is reduced in the second and third Li zone due to moderation of neutrons and LiAl regions with high densities.

The excitation energy for the Pb-208 isotope is 2.6125 MeV for neutrons. The higher energetic fusion neutrons can occur inelastic collision and thereby split into smaller nuclei or can produce new neutrons. Since the emitted neutron energy is higher after the inelastic collision, the tritium production rate is lower in the lithium zones in comparison with the situation when the uranium multiplier is used.

When no multiplier is used, the tritium production rate solely depends upon the moderator region. The multiplier is not used therefore neutrons generated from fusion pass the lower number of neutrons compared to the situation when uranium and lead multiplier are used. The neutrons need to be moderated to increase the production of tritium. Because the ${}^6\text{Li}(n,\alpha)\text{T}$ reaction cross section is low with high energetic neutrons. That is why, the tritium production rate is the highest in the third lithium zone due to better moderation compared to the 1st and 2nd lithium zone.

Therefore, the use of a uranium multiplier enhances the overall tritium production rate in three different lithium zones cumulatively. Further study is conducted focusing on the materials' effect of neutron-induced radiation.

Figure 6. ${}^6\text{Li}(n,\alpha)\text{T}$ reaction cross section (Soppera et al. 2014).

Figure 7. Tritium production rate in 3 separate Li zones.

Relative activation rate in uranium multiplier

Fig. 8 represents the relative activation rate for different types of neutron-induced disintegration reactions for various detectors from the neutron-producing target layer. The result from the detectors can be used to analyze the effect of material interactions to a single neutron as well as ensure the simulation or analysis matches what would happen in real-world scenarios (Madland 1982; Glebov et al. 2006; Soppera et al. 2014; Jakhar et al. 2015; Tonghua et al. 2019). Table 3 shows cross-section values at the neutron energy level of 14.75 MeV as well as the threshold values for the corresponding neutron-induced disintegration reactions. The relative activation rate is calculated by dividing the activation value measured at each detector position by the activation value measured at the first detector position.

In Fig. 8 and the corresponding relation with Table 3, the study shows that the relative activation rate of $\text{In-115}(n,n')$ is the highest since the threshold energy for this reaction is the lowest. Though with the energy of 14.75 MeV for neutrons ejected from D-T reactions, the cross-section

Figure 8. Relative activation rate distribution in the axial channel of the blanket mock up with uranium multiplier.

Table 3. Cross section at 14.75 MeV energy value and threshold energy value for the various reaction types

Reaction Type	Cross-section (barns) (Soppera et al. 2014)	Threshold energy (MeV) (Center 2020)
${}^{63}\text{Cu}(n,2n){}^{62}\text{Cu}$	0.4541	11.0
${}^{65}\text{Cu}(n,2n){}^{64}\text{Cu}$	0.906	10
${}^{64}\text{Zn}(n,2n){}^{63}\text{Zn}$	0.1117	12.5
${}^{56}\text{Fe}(n,p){}^{56}\text{Mn}$	0.1144	3
${}^{27}\text{Al}(n,p){}^{27}\text{Mg}$	0.07205	1.9
${}^{107}\text{Ag}(n,2n){}^{106m}\text{Ag}$	1.351	9.63
${}^{115}\text{In}(n,n'){}^{115m}\text{In}$	0.2116	0.5
${}^{204}\text{Pb}(n,n'){}^{204m}\text{Pb}$	0.306	2.2

for the ${}^{204}\text{Pb}(n,n'){}^{204m}\text{Pb}$ reaction is 0.306 barns, much higher than the cross-section of the ${}^{27}\text{Al}(n,p){}^{27}\text{Mg}$ reaction which is 0.07205 barns, that is why the activation rate for the reaction ${}^{204}\text{Pb}(n,n'){}^{204m}\text{Pb}$ is higher even though the threshold energy is higher compared to the ${}^{27}\text{Al}(n,p){}^{27}\text{Mg}$ reaction (Soppera et al. 2014). For the same reason, the activation rate is higher for the ${}^{56}\text{Fe}(n,p){}^{56}\text{Mn}$ reaction with lower threshold energy compared to the

$^{63}\text{Cu}(n,2n)^{62}\text{Cu}$, $^{65}\text{Cu}(n,2n)^{64}\text{Cu}$, and $^{107}\text{Ag}(n,2n)^{106\text{m}}\text{Ag}$. Though $^{63}\text{Cu}(n,2n)^{62}\text{Cu}$ and $^{65}\text{Cu}(n,2n)^{64}\text{Cu}$ reaction have better cross section. The activation rate of $^{64}\text{Zn}(n,2n)^{63}\text{Zn}$ reaction is the lowest with a relatively lower cross-section value and with the highest threshold energy.

Conclusion

The SERPENT Monte Carlo Algorithm is utilized in order to carry out the computational modelling of the blanket mock up for the fusion-fission hybrid reactor construction. Due to the fact that the deviations from the experimental results obtained for the reactions $^{63}\text{Cu}(n,2n)^{62}\text{Cu}$ and $^{65}\text{Cu}(n,2n)^{64}\text{Cu}$ are significantly lower than the value of 10%, the simulation result is verified with the experimental result.

Within the context of the blanket mock-up, the utilization of multiplier serves the objective of increasing the rate of generation of tritium. Tritium is the fuel for the fusion D-T reaction hence it is necessary. In compared to the case of lead multiplier and the situation in which there is no multiplier at all, the research indicates that the utilization of uranium multiplier has the potential to increase the production of tritium by 1.86 times and 3.38 times respectively. The cross-sectional data that were received from the ENDF/B-VII.I

cross section library can be used to provide an explanation with regard to the cause of such an incidence. The creation of tritium in three distinct lithium zones for the purpose of utilizing uranium multiplier will be at its highest. This is due to the fact that U-238 possesses a bigger cross section for multiplying the neutron number through the quick fission reaction with the incident neutron emitted from the fusion reaction. It is possible to forecast the behavior of the material in the event that it is subjected to neutron-induced fission by analyzing the activation rate of certain isotopes. According to the fact that the utilization of uranium multiplier results in a bigger multiplication of neutron numbers, the activation rate is computed for the utilization of uranium multiplier. It is because of the difference in the threshold energy to initiate the neutron activation and also the cross section of that particular reaction at the 14.75 MeV neutron energy level that isotopes have different activation rates. This discrepancy is the reason why isotopes have different activation rates.

This research effort demonstrates that the utilization of uranium multiplier has the potential to enhance the production of tritium, which, in turn, has the potential to lessen the uncertainty associated with the creation of tritium from ^6Li isotope. This finding sets the path for further computational research in the event that hybrid reactor blanket analysis is performed.

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